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FORMATION OF PHYSICAL ASPECTS IN GENERAL AND PERSONAL PHYSICAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *this article will talk about the formation of a healthy lifestyle in society, strengthening the health of the population, wide involvement of the population in physical education and sports activities. A healthy lifestyle-studies the health complex of the life and functioning of the body, as well as tissue cells, but also with physical education.*

Keywords: *sports, mass sports, general physical fitness, special physical fitness, healthy lifestyle .*

Introduction

In our country, physical education and sports play a significant role in strengthening the health of young people, improving their physical fitness, and developing their capacity for defending the homeland and engaging in productive work. Physical education and sports are fundamental tools for the comprehensive physical development of individuals. In institutions specializing in physical education and sports, lessons in physical education aim to enhance students' agility, strength, and endurance, study the impact of the workload on the body, and ensure the effectiveness of these lessons by introducing new pedagogical technologies into the analysis process. These tasks are among the pressing issues of today.

In our society, fostering a healthy lifestyle, creating conditions that meet modern requirements for the regular involvement of the population, especially the younger generation, in physical education and mass sports, and through sports competitions, reinforcing their confidence in their willpower, strength, and capabilities, as well as cultivating courage, patriotism, and loyalty to the motherland, are all being systematically organized. Additionally, wide-ranging efforts are being made to further develop physical education and mass sports and to select talented athletes from among the youth.

Currently, across all regions of our country, promoting the importance of mass sports in the lives of individuals and families, as well as its role as a foundation for physical and mental well-being, is a priority. Important and pressing tasks include creating the necessary conditions for individuals to develop their abilities and talents, selecting talented athletes, and refining the system for their targeted

preparation. It is particularly important to engage young children and those entering life with great hope in mass and independent physical activities from an early age, to strengthen them, and to pay serious attention to their growth into healthy, strong, resilient, and agile individuals.

In students' general and personal physical training, the development of physical aspects should involve regular engagement in sports, enhancing general and specialized physical fitness, and active participation in mass sports competitions. In addition, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 24, 2020, "On Measures to Further Improve and Popularize Physical Education and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan," outlines the main directions for reforming the physical education and sports system by 2025, aiming to increase the percentage of the population regularly engaged in physical education and sports to 30%. Sport, which is an integral part of physical culture, is a method and tool of physical education, involving the organization, preparation, and conduct of competitions in various complexes of physical exercises. The goal of sport is to strengthen individuals' health, achieve high results and victories in sports competitions, and promote overall physical development. The first sports competitions were held in Greece. After the establishment of the International Olympic Committee, sports began to develop rapidly.

The cultural life of the people is rich and diverse, and it cannot be separated from sports. Sports can elevate the spiritual life of individuals. By focusing on physical exercises and maintaining a healthy body, young people can better dedicate their minds and bodies to learning. Through sports, students can regularly activate their bodies and minds, learn to cooperate in team activities, enhance their understanding without words, experience competition and pressure in conflicts, satisfy their internal needs, and enjoy the emotional experiences that sports provide.

There are three main interrelated organizational forms of sports:

1. Mass amateur sports;
2. Sports as an academic discipline;
3. High-performance sports.

Mass amateur sports contribute to an individual's physical improvement and are limited by age, health status, and physical development level. Sports as an academic discipline are included in the military-physical training programs of all types of educational institutions and armed forces. High-performance sports create conditions for achieving the best sports results (records), demonstrate physical preparedness, and help apply effective methods of physical training in mass practice.

Physical activity significantly impacts the condition of the central nervous system. The formula "a healthy mind in a healthy body" remains relevant and has long served humanity's interests. Movement is a physiological need of the human being, embedded in their genetic program. Some exercises can induce a unique psychological state, reduce psycho-emotional stress, improve mood, and enhance mental activity .

When engaged in sports, blood circulation is stimulated, and deep breathing helps supply the brain with blood and oxygen. It also improves an individual's concentration. Physical exercises gradually relieve nervous tension, resulting in a sense of joy: nothing hurts, there are no illnesses, and all organs function normally. This feeling of joy, in turn, creates a good mood. Consider the impact of physical activity not only on physical condition but also on mental capacity. However, it is known that these concepts are inseparable, especially since physical activity affects the entire body, not selectively. The organic basis of the interrelationship between these areas lies in the unity of an individual's physical and spiritual development. Typically, physical activity is distinguished by its biological, pedagogical, psychological, and social impacts on the human body (health, physical development, physical fitness,

mental self-control characteristics, social status, behavioral style) .

Promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people, strengthening their health, and making meaningful use of their free time are among the important tasks of today. Therefore, mass sports competitions are being organized on a wide scale. These sports competitions are organized across various sports.

To further strengthen student youth, we need to enhance their general and specialized physical training. General physical training is a primary means of improving physical health. General physical training mainly enables the achievement of the following tasks:

- Ensuring the comprehensive development of the human body, developing physical qualities such as endurance, strength, speed, flexibility, and agility, and creating a functional base necessary for the physical development of students based on the development of these qualities.
- Strengthening health and counteracting the harmful factors of the external environment.
- Creating conditions for active rest during periods of reduced work capacity in academic and labor activities.
- Strengthening willpower in overcoming additional challenges. Physical fitness is the level at which a student can fully realize all the creative potential of their physical development, movement knowledge, and skills. It is important to note that an individual's physical qualities are closely interconnected, and it is incorrect to apply exercises aimed solely at developing a specific quality. At the same time, physical exercises positively impact the student's physical development.

Among the means of general physical training, exercises performed on bars, parallel bars, and with various dumbbells are more effective for physical development. These exercises ensure body harmony. A set of physical exercises aimed at increasing muscle mass, creating a beautiful figure, and improving external respiration preserves and strengthens the health of young people.

Special physical training:

The history of special physical training dates back to three thousand years ago when the Zoroastrians (in present-day Khorezm oasis and its surroundings) engaged in special physical training exercises to raise children spiritually and physically. Such examples are also reflected in the "Alpomish" epic and the "Tomiris Legend." Especially, the process of special preparation for military valor had practical significance in the lives of the great commander Amir Temur and his descendants (Mirzo Ulugbek, Babur, etc.). In general, there are countless and extensive services and activities in the path of military courage, heroism, craft, and honor, as depicted in historical sources, literary works, and images. The advantages of special physical training, connected with physical qualities, are aimed at physically strengthening and developing specific parts of the human body (hands, feet, back, etc.). The physical education activities, especially the MJT (special physical training) exercises, should be conducted in the following directions:

- Fast running (60, 100 meters).
- High jump and long jump.
- Hurdle jumps.
- Throwing a ball far and accurately.
- Pull-ups on a horizontal bar.
- Performing acrobatic exercises in wrestling training.
- Performing elements of sports games.

The positive impact of special physical training is observed through the completion of assigned tasks and objectives. If the indicators and results are positive, with good growth rates, additional

exercises can be assigned as tasks. Students should constantly improve the skills they acquire during lessons, which will lead to purposeful use in subsequent processes and open the way to perfecting the above-mentioned physical qualities (speed, agility, dexterity, strength, endurance) and the methods used .

A healthy lifestyle should unify all the methods mentioned above into one system. Such a task envisages the broad connection of a healthy lifestyle with specialized medical sciences, general pathology, biochemistry, genetics, specialized biology, ecology, anthropology, social sciences, economics, physics, and chemistry. However, first of all, it is necessary to establish a connection with the physiology of a healthy and diseased organism.

A healthy lifestyle considers the life and activity of the body, as well as the tissues and cells, and includes the complex of health-promoting measures, including physical education.

The concept of a healthy lifestyle, which is associated with a significant deterioration in health and well-being, developed further in the last decade of the 20th century. The subject of a healthy lifestyle encompasses individual health and human health reserves, as well as the pre-illness state of a person. The object of a healthy lifestyle is practically healthy people, as well as all individuals in the pre-illness state, regardless of age, and in terms of psychological, socio-cultural, and other aspects.

A healthy lifestyle is a process of forming value-oriented guidelines for health and a healthy lifestyle, which are established as an integral part of life values and a universal cultural worldview.

In the process of healthy lifestyle education, an individual develops a conscious attitude towards health, based on positive interests and needs, an intellectual perception of and relationship with society, creativity, enrichment of the spiritual world, self-improvement of their health, and careful treatment of the health of those around them .

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In the process of promoting a healthy lifestyle, an individual develops a conscious attitude towards health based on positive interests and needs, an intellectual connection and relationship with society, creativity, enrichment of the spiritual world, improvement of their own health, and careful treatment of the health of those around them. In conclusion, it can be seen that the main basis for increasing the general and personal physical preparedness of young people is the organization of mass sports competitions and the development of general and specialized physical training. At the same time, students' cognitive knowledge is formed and enhanced through physical culture values, helping to prevent diseases that may be related to their future professions.

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